

Data from: Reproducibility of the Quantification of Reversible Wall Interactions in VOC Sampling Lines

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Citation

Sassi, G.; Khan, B.A. and Lecuna, M. (2021). Data from: Reproducibility of the Quantification of Reversible Wall Interactions in VOC Sampling Lines. Zenodo, Dataset, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5541756>

Publication available in:

<https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos12020280>

Abstract

In the paper, a method to quantify the amount of substance segregated by reversible interactions on sampling lines is proposed. The areic amount of a VOC (Acetone) interacting with the pipe is measured for a commercial test pipe (Sulfinert®) as the amount of substance per unit area of the internal surface of the test pipe segregated from the flowing gas mixture. The areic amount is function of numerical integrals estimated under different conditions and reproducibility is evaluated. The data used to estimate the integrals described in this work is organised in folders. Each folder correspond to a sample. Sample information is available Table 3 of the paper:

Table 3. Sulfinert® Number of experiments, pipe lengths, and test condition ranges (residence time, temperature, pressure, and Reynolds number).

Sample	N	L (m)	$q_{V_g}^{0_g}$ (SmL min ⁻¹)	τ_r (min)	T (°C)	P (kPa)	Re (-)
Sulfinert A	53	26	9–195	0.5–9.5	22–27	100–130	5–150
Sulfinert B	29	8.5	9–55	0.6–3.2	17–30	100–120	5–40
Sulfinert C	18	8.5	9–55	0.6–3.2	20–22	100–120	5–40

How to read the data

- Each folder contains a .txt file named 'Integral'+Sample letter (A/B/C) that contains in columns: experiment ID, date, recording starting time, estimated integral (min), the flowrate set at the beginning of the run (Sml/min), Temperature (°C), Pressure (Pa abs).
- Integral values are calculated as according to equation (6) of the paper. The whole data from each experiment was used. The integration times are from each starting point till peak minus the integral of the bias (as described in the paper).
- Experiment IDs combine a reference to the flowrate and a sequential number.

IDs	Flowrate (Sml/min)	IDs	Flowrate (Sml/min)
1-9	9	101-107	100
11-17	15	151-156	150
21-28	25	201-208	196
31-39	35		

4. Each folder contains 3 .mat files per each experiment ID, named:
 - *ID+ 'Value.mat'*: instant value of signal in [mV] for that specific experiment.
 - *ID+ 'VaN.mat'*: instant value of signal, normalized, for that specific experiment.
 - *ID+ 'Time.mat'*: time from switch till equilibrium establishes, for that specific experiment.
5. Values are reported from the starting point of the switch (ts3 in figure 3 of the paper) till assumed equilibrium after 10 minutes in order to have same length of dataset (till a point before ts5 of the figure 3 of the paper).

Materials and Methods

- Zero gas: Certified clean dry air cylinder (purity N5.5) by SIAD
- Gas Mixture: Certified acetone in air gas cylinders by SIAD; expanded uncertainties ($k = 2$) indicated in the paper.
- Instruments/components: LNE certified sonic nozzles, Swagelok valves, Bronkhorst certified Mass Flowmeter (MFM), Calibrated Pt100 (brand N/A), Air Liquid pressure reducer, Gas Chromatograph (GC, Bruker GC-450)/Flame Ionization Detector (FID).
- Materials: Pressure regulators, sonic nozzles and valves are in stainless steel (uncoated). Pressure regulators and sonic nozzles in both the VOC and zero gas line, are permanently flushed by the mixture so they are considered to be in equilibrium. Only 4-way valves are in contact with both zero gas and VOC mixture, however the area of contact is small enough for it to be negligible. Capillaries were in fused silica and the rest of the lines in the system was made of coated stainless steel.

Traceability

All the calculations in the work are function of the FID reading (GC/FID reading without column) vs time. The method as described in the paper could be applied to any kind of signal directly proportional to the amount fraction, as long as the system is sensitive to the VOC and amount fraction level in the tested VOC mixture.

The paper focus on the evaluation of reproducibility, meaning reversible interactions were quantified under different conditions and results compared. The evaluation of the accuracy of the estimation is not a part of this work.

A certified mixture cylinder was used to perform the experiments to provide a VOC and zero gas source stable in the short term. The experimental setup is built to allow fast valve switches between VOC and zero gas; and between the test tubing and a short pipe (called bypass). The stability of the measurement system is given by the stable FID signals of zero air and VOC mixture through the bypass.

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Funding

This work is part of the project 19ENV06 MetClimVOC, which has received funding from the European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) cofinanced by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

Code

Open source languages can be used to read the .mat files, such as Python:

```
from scipy.io import loadmat

x = loadmat('../input/Data_Sample_A/1Time.mat')
y = loadmat('../input/Data_Sample_A/1Value.mat')
z = loadmat('../input/Data_Sample_A/1VaN.mat')

list1 = [[element for element in upperElement] for upperElement in x['tt']]
list2 = [[element for element in upperElement] for upperElement in y['vv']]
list3 = [[element for element in upperElement] for upperElement in z['Cn']]
```